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| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
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Cracking Performance of asphalt binders and mixtures with rejuvenator: the Kielsbroek case study

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Outline

- I Context and Research Problem
- II Research Objectives and Questions
- III Materials
- IV Methods
- V Results and Analysis
- VI Conclusions and Recommendations

I. Context and Research Problem

① RAP

② Rejuvenator

③ WMA

II. Research Objectives and Questions

How do rejuvenators influence the cracking performance of asphalt mixtures and binders with high RAP contents?

1

How are the rheological properties of high-RAP binders affected by rejuvenators?

2

How is the cracking performance of high-RAP asphalt mixtures influenced by rejuvenators?

3

Can rejuvenators enable reduced production temperatures in high-RAP mixtures while maintaining equivalent performance?

4

To what extent do improvements observed at the binder level translate into enhanced performance at the mixture level?

III. Materials: Mixture Level

ID	Description	RAP (%)	Compaction (°C)	PEN (0,1mm)
S-REF	AC10 surf reference	40	175	30
S-RJ	AC10 surf + rejuvenator		175	50
S-RJW	AC10 surf + rejuvenator (warm mix)		150	50
B-REF	AC14 base reference	70	175	23
B-RJ	AC14 base + rejuvenator		175	40
B-RJW	AC14 base + rejuvenator (warm mix)		150	40

III. Materials: Binder Level

IV. Methods

V. Experimental Results: Binder Level

Penetration

V. Experimental Results: Binder Level

Frequency sweeps
4, 8, 25 mm (-30°C ~ 80°C)

V. Experimental Results: Binder Level

Frequency sweeps
4, 8, 25 mm (-30°C ~ 80°C)

V. Experimental Results: Mixture Level

Air voids

V. Experimental Results: Mixture Level

ITS
(15°C, 50 mm/min)

V. Experimental Results: Mixture Level

SCB
(0°C and 25°C, 5 mm/min)

■ 25°C ▨ 0°C

VI. Conclusions and Recommendations

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V. Experimental Results: Mixture Level

SCB
(0°C and 25°C, 5 mm/min)

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